

Rac-3o

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-159-rac-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1026
Vial:	55	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2159 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	25.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/26/2021 4:46:12 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2021 5:16:22 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	18.524	6476700	49.26	193897
2	21.277	6671291	50.74	

Asy-3o (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-161-2-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	71	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 160 2
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/25/2021 4:57:13 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2021 5:20:53 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	18.577	841503	2.90	25243
2	21.244	28203690	97.10	748004